

USING NEW ITEMS ON LISTENING LESSONS

Eshmamatova Saygul Allaberdiyevna

Kashkadaryo region Dehkanabad district

English teacher of the school N-35.

Abstract: *The research samples were taken using cluster random sampling, with the total number of samples being 60 students. The location of this research was SMA Angkasa 2 Jakarta. The research methodology adopted was quasi-experimental method, with the research design being post-test only control group design. To collect the data, the students were given objective test, numbering 30 items. The research data were analyzed descriptively and inferentially.*

Key words: *Podcast, Listening, Listening Comprehension.*

English has been a global language since long ago. English plays an important role in the international interaction. English is also important in education because English is a language of science. There are so many scientific books were written in English for gaining knowledge. English is also one of the most studied languages all across the world, most of the countries teach it as a second language from primary school. Because of those reasons, students need to know English to excel in science and education. There are four skills of English subject that must be learnt by Senior High School students. They are listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening is one of the important skills in teaching and learning English because speaking without listening first are impossible. It is in accordance with opinion of Rost (1994, p.107), points out there are four language skills: listening,

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students also had a problem in length and speed of listening. Next, students could not write what they listen correctly. The last, the listening input by the teachers is rudimentary (as cited in Sabouri, 2016, p.127) Based on the explanation above, to overcome those problems, teachers need to know what media to teach English in listening class and teachers should think carefully about how to make the activities going to be successful and also make the interesting content. There are many kinds of media in teaching listening. Podcast is one of media that can improve listening skill. According to Constantine (2007), Podcast was first known in 2004, and it is defined as an internet audio blogging or internet audio publishing. The audio recording is designed to be downloaded and listened to on a portable mp3 player or on a computer. Podcasts are delivered online automatically via a website, so it is different from other audios. Podcasts offer a ‘real-life listening’ source that all foreign language listeners are allowed to benefit from it. The importance of using Podcasts is all learners can benefit from global listening even if they only listen three or five minutes in a day. In accordance with listening activity, there was a research conducted by Rizzi, Rothwell, Nie and Edirisingha (2007) entitled “Podcasting to Provide Teaching and Learning Support for an Undergraduate Module on English Language and Communication at Kingston University”. The study describes the teaching and learning context and how the Podcasts enhance their ability in listening. Inspired and triggered by the usefulness and benefits of the Podcast as teaching media discussed above, which have been verified empirically by several writers, the writer would like to conduct the research in the same area in an effort to investigate whether Podcast can also effect on the grade ten students’ listening comprehension at SMA Angkasa 2, Jakarta, in the Academic

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